

Synthesis of amides from carboxylic acids and urea in the presence of pyridine under microwave irradiation

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A very simple and efficient procedure for the synthesis of primary amides from carboxylic acids and urea in presence of pyridine under microwave irradiation is described. Various amides were prepared within 20–30 s and in excellent yields.

There are several different routes for the preparation of carboxamides¹. In most of the cases either a complex and expensive reagent is involved or the reaction takes a long time for completion.

In recent years, the application of microwave technology in organic chemistry has been explored extensively. Microwave irradiation often leads to a remarkable shorter reaction time, increased yields, easier work up matching with green chemistry protocols. More recently, there have been some reports which describe the preparation of primary, secondary and tertiary amides under microwave assisted solvent free condition². Under microwave irradiation generally a homogeneous solid mixture is taken for the reaction and the time required for such reactions is comparatively longer when compared to heterogeneous reaction of solid and liquid mixture as the reported methods involve use of solid mixture in the synthesis of amides, reaction of the later type has attracted our interest. Recently, we have reported the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones/thiones from araldehydes/urea or thiourea using catalytic amount of ZnCl₂ via. Biginelli reaction under microwave conditions³. In this paper, we wish to report that primary amides can be obtained readily from carboxylic acid and urea in the presence of pyridine under microwave irradiation within 20–30 s (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the chemicals were purchased from B.D.H./Merck and used as received. Reactions were monitored on TLC by comparison with the authentic samples. For the microwave irradiation experiments described below, a conventional (unmodified) household microwave oven was used (LG Electronics India Private Limited). Yields refer to the isolated yields of the products. The IR spectra of the products were recorded on NICOLET 400D FT-IR spectrophotometer. M.p.s. were determined on a Buchi melting point apparatus.

General procedure for synthesis of primary amides : A mixture of carboxylic acid (1 mmol) and urea (2 mmol) was ground well at 25°C, and was taken into a Pyrex cylindrical tube, pyridine (1 mmol) was then added, homogenized and irradiated in a domestic MW oven (320 W). At the end of irradiation (20–30 s), the mixture was cooled to room temperature and extracted with EtOAc or chloroform. The extract was washed successively with a solution of dilute HCl, 5% NaHCO₃ and water. The organic layer was dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed under vacuum. The crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography using 15% EtOAc in light petroleum as an eluent.

Results and discussion

In a typical experiment, equimolar quantities of urea and carboxylic acid were ground to a fine powder at room temperature (25°C), pyridine was then added to the above mixture. The resulting mixture was homogenized and subjected to microwave irradiation (20–30 s, 320 W) to get an amide in quantitative yield. In order to standardize and extend this reaction for the preparation of different amides, different carboxylic acids were subjected to MW irradiation.

Table 1. Synthesis of primary amides from carboxylic acids and urea in the presence of pyridine under microwave irradiation

Entry	Acid	Time (s)	Product ^a	Yield (%) ^b	M.p °C (lit. ¹⁷)
1		92	127–129 (129.1)		
2		85	160 (160)		
3		93	176–179 (179)		
4		65	160–161 (162)		
5		92	200–201 (201)		
6		90	165–166 (166)		
7		93	134–135 (135)		
8		89	94–95 (95)		
9		68	169–170 (170)		
10		70	141–142 (142)		

^aProducts were characterized by their melting points and IR special analysis. ^bYields refer to isolated pure products.

tion with urea in the presence of pyridine and the results are presented in Table 1. Under the above reaction conditions, the reaction is expected to proceed first by the formation of a pyridinium carboxylate salt. This salt may increase the absorption of the microwave energy and this energy absorption increment may cause the pyrolysis of urea and liberation of ammonia. In the second step, the pyridine may get exchanged by ammonia to form the ammonium carboxylate salt and finally strong heating of the ammonium carboxylate salt can give the corresponding carboxamide.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, the present microwave irradiation procedure provides an efficient and very simple method for the preparation of primary amides using urea, carboxylic acids and pyridine in excellent yields.

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References

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